

ANANDA COOMARASWAMY'S PHILOSOPHY OF TRADITIONALISM: UNDERSTANDING TRADITION THROUGH ART

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Abstract: In this article, the author explores the teachings of Ananda Coomaraswamy from a traditionalist perspective. By taking a broader view of traditionalism, the author highlights how Coomaraswamy illuminates the connection between tradition and art through Eastern and Western cultural lenses. For Coomaraswamy, art represents an essential aspect of the spiritual legacy of civilizations, infused with the essence of tradition. It is this appeal to traditional art, he argues, that offers a path out of the contemporary spiritual crisis of society.

Keywords: tradition, traditionalism, art, symbolism, culture, civilization, East and West, intercultural dialogue.

In the philosophy of the 20th century, studies in Eastern and Western cultures were updated, which directly influenced various social and humanitarian sciences. As a result, cultural anthropology became an independent field, incorporating studies in anthropology, history, cultural studies, ethnology, and ethnography [1, p.315]. The anthropological approach to social and humanitarian sciences during this period is exemplified by the emergence of philosophical anthropology. However, due to the broad disciplinary boundaries of philosophy, there is also a trend in comparative philosophy within the context of research on Eastern and Western culture. The methodological tools of this field include a variety of methods not only from the philosophical sciences, but also from other fields of social and humanitarian knowledge. By exploring the East and West, representatives of comparative

philosophy discover aspects that bring these two cultures closer and allow for an intercultural dialogue. One such important aspect for this dialogue is the phenomenon of tradition, which acquires a different interpretation in the context of comparative philosophy. It is worth noting that the emphasis on a comparative study of tradition was made by the philosopher of the 20th century Rene Guenon, who is considered the main advocate of integral traditionalism.

At its core, traditionalism sees perennialism as a way to overcome the spiritual crisis of modernity, through an appeal to past cultural experiences [2, p.84]. This is because both Guenon and traditionalists believe that the modern world is facing a widespread spiritual crisis. The concept of tradition, as interpreted by Guenon, is a transcendental truth that speaks to its religious nature [3, p.96]. However, W.Dickson argues that the “truth” Guenon refers to is a metaphysical one [4, p.589]. This suggests that tradition is a complex concept with philosophical, cultural, political, and historical dimensions. For example, in terms of cultural understanding, we refer to those traditions and customs that bring societies of the East and West together. In the political context, this means that there are similarities in political processes between these two regions. Philosophically, traditions have a wide range of interpretations, covering both exoteric and esoteric aspects of tradition. This includes various world religions and their irrational teachings. Another prominent representative of traditionalism, Ananda Coomaraswamy, discusses the manifestation of tradition in art from both the East and West.

So, Coomaraswamy saw art as a way to express spiritual and metaphysical truths. He believed that true art should convey sacred meanings and symbols that help people understand deeper levels of reality. In his view, art was an important part of traditional cultures, serving both aesthetic and spiritual purposes [5]. At the same time, he saw art as an opposition to materialism and modernism. Representatives of traditionalism, like Kumaraswamy, were critical of modernity and its materialistic approach to life. He pointed out that modern art had lost its spiritual guidance and become a mere commodity, devoid of meaning and content. Only traditional art could resist these trends, as it retained sacred aspects and spiritual depth. Therefore,

Coomaraswamy saw a way to overcome the crisis and rebuild the tradition through the study and promotion of traditional art, which is an integral part of the spiritual wealth and heritage of any civilization. It should be noted that, for Coomaraswamy, art is not an isolated element of social life, unconnected to it in any way. On the contrary, art is part of culture, permeated with society’s way of life and the spirit of tradition. In this sense, art contributes to the integration of the East and the West. Therefore, art can be seen as an expression of tradition, and it can also act as a “conveyor” of traditional wisdom. It is well known that art plays a significant role in the development of individuals and society, as it influences the worldview and perspective of individuals through aesthetic aspects. Through art, one can transmit spiritual knowledge and values, develop a sense of beauty, and gain an understanding of cultural traditions. Coomaraswamy argued that a proper education should include studying traditional art as a means of spiritual and cultural enrichment [5, p.13].

Due to the importance of tradition and comparative philosophy in the dialogue between cultures, it is essential to provide specific examples that were mentioned by Coomaraswamy. For instance, he pointed out the significance of the mandala symbol in Buddhist art and the rose motif in Gothic cathedrals, both of which represent cosmic order and harmony. The mandala, a sacred geometric design, symbolizes the universe in Buddhism, while the rose, often found in stained glass windows, represents perfection and eternity in Western Gothic art. Additionally, the tree of life is a common symbol that connects heaven, earth, and the underworld in various cultural traditions, including Celtic art and Hindu and Buddhist beliefs. If we turn to music, Kumarasamy drew attention to the fact that Gregorian chants and Indian ragas are both musical styles designed for meditation and creating a spiritual atmosphere. These styles have deep roots in religious practice and are used to help people immerse themselves in a spiritual state. In addition, Indian epics like the “Mahabharata” and Greek myths not only serve as entertainment, but also convey deep moral and spiritual lessons. Coomaraswamy also drew attention to the architecture of the East and West, pointing out that in both civilizations, it reflects sacred and cosmic principles. Hindu temples and Gothic cathedrals, for example,

were built with cosmological and sacred principles in mind. Hindu temples are planned according to the mandala, which symbolizes the universe, while Gothic cathedrals are designed to direct the gaze upwards towards the sky, symbolizing a path to God. Sacred geometry is present in both to create harmonious and proportionate buildings that reflect the divine order.

Representatives of the philosophy of traditionalism, such as Rene Guenon, Ananda Coomaraswamy, Michel Valsan, Julius Evola and Frithjof Schuon, consider various aspects of the phenomenon of tradition. While the general foundation is based on the teachings of Rene Guenon, tradition is interpreted differently by each of these thinkers. Guenon sees tradition as a metaphysical concept, while Coomaraswamy understands tradition through the lens of art, which sets him apart from other traditionalists. Ananda Coomaraswamy placed great importance on art, seeing it as a means of expressing spiritual truths and opposing materialism. He saw art as a source of symbolic and iconographic knowledge that could help restore respect for traditional cultures and play an important role in education and upbringing. The works of Ananda Coomaraswamy continue to be significant for those seeking a deeper understanding of the significance of art in human life and culture.

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